

Dynamic concentration factor: A novel parameter for the rigorous evaluation of solar compound parabolic collectors

Jose Moreno-SanSegundo, Miguel Martín-Sómer, Javier Marugán *

Department of Chemical and Environmental Technology, ESCET, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, C/Tulipán s/n, Móstoles, Madrid 28933, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Solar-driven photoactivated processes have proven to be effective technologies for removing pathogens and chemical contaminants from water. Reflector systems are commonly used to concentrate the sunlight and improve their efficiency. Among them, compound parabolic collectors (CPC) are the most widely used, being the concentration factor (CF), their main design parameter, calculated directly from the geometry. This work presents the development of a novel parameter, called dynamic concentration factor (DCF), to assess the efficiency of a CPC as a function of the solar vector (the beam angle depends on location, season of the year and time of the day) and the reflective properties of the material. The DCF is defined as the ratio between the incident radiation reaching the receiver with and without the collector. DCF of CPC with different acceptance angles have been calculated with a ray-tracing tool and validated with experimental data from actinometry reactions. Analysis of the results has been done by plotting the dependence of the DCF versus the beam angle for increasing reflectivity indexes. This facilitates the estimation of the total radiation available to conduct a photoactivated process, whose reaction rate is proportional to the incident photons in the receiver. Global worldwide results using time-varying local solar irradiation data showed that, although the CPC with an acceptance angle of 90° ($CF = 1$) is commonly assumed as an optimal configuration due to its ability to concentrate diffuse radiation, the use of CPC with different acceptance angles could be more suitable in some regions of the planet.

1. Introduction

Solar photoactivated processes have been shown as highly efficient and environmentally friendly water treatments [1]. These processes are based on the use of solar light (mainly UV light) as a source of energy, showing great efficiency in the removal of a large number of recalcitrant chemical compounds to other treatments [2–7], as well as to carry out pathogens disinfection [8–14]. Their mechanism can be either photolytic (by direct absorption of photons by the substances or microorganisms) or mediated by the generation of highly oxidizing species, such as hydroxyl radicals. In both cases, the rate of the process is obviously connected to the amount of photons incident to the system, and therefore to the available solar irradiance and the radiation collection efficiency.

Solar irradiance at the Earth's surface varies significantly with the position of the Sun (solar vector) as a function of the geocoordinates (latitude and longitude), date and time [15]. Moreover, atmospheric attenuation strongly depends also on weather conditions [16,17]. The global solar radiation received on the Earth's surface can be divided into

two components, direct and diffuse [18]. Direct radiation is constituted by the photons who suffer no interaction with the atmosphere, whereas diffuse radiation reaches the ground level with a different direction from that corresponding to the position of the Sun due to the light scattering that takes place when crossing the atmosphere.

To increase the available radiation, several solar light concentration systems have been developed over the years [19,20]. Depending on their purpose, the geometry of the collectors is more or less sophisticated, being their fundamental design parameter the concentration factor (CF), which represents the degree of multiplication of the naturally available solar irradiance.

Due to their importance in photoactivated water treatment processes, compound parabolic collectors (CPC) deserve a separate mention. CPC are fixed concentrators with a reflective surface made from the double composition of a parabola. Their main advantage is the capability of concentrating both direct and a large part of diffuse radiation that falls within the so-called acceptance angle (θ) [20,21] without requiring a solar tracking system. The radiation reaching the opening area is reflected towards the tubular reactor, illuminating the entire circumference of the tube [22]. The CPC most commonly used in water

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: javier.marugan@urjc.es (J. Marugán).

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Nomenclature	
<i>Collectors, reactors, and optical parameters</i>	
CPC	Compound Parabolic Collector
θ	Acceptance angle. Rays with an incidence angle higher than this value do not reach the reactor tube (rad).
r	Reflectivity of the collector material (dimensionless). 1.0 is total reflection, while 0.0 is null reflection. Specular reflection was considered in all cases.
R	Radius of the reactor tube (m)
κ	Absorption coefficient of the medium in the reactor tube (m^{-1}).
OD	Optical density of the medium, product of the radius of the reactor tube by the absorption coefficient of the medium (dimensionless).
<i>Ray-tracing variables</i>	
α	Incidence angle. Angle between the original direction of the incident ray (before any bounce on the collector) and the normal vector to the collector opening surface (rad).
E, E_a, E_b	Energy carried by a single ray (W m^{-2}). Subindex a means after crossing the reactor tube, while b means before crossing it.
$L, L_i, L_{i,j}$	Path length of a ray i crossing the reactor tube (m). If j appears, is the path length of ray i at bounce j .
$b_i(\alpha)$	Number of bounces of a ray on the reflecting surface of the collector. (dimensionless).
n	Number of emitted rays (dimensionless).
Δx	Width of each ray in the collector opening surface (the division of the total width over the number of rays) (m).
q	Radiation flux. Radiant energy crossing a surface differential per unit time (W m^{-2}).
Q	Radiation flow. Radiant energy crossing a whole surface per unit time (W).
G	Incident radiation. Flux of photons travelling in any direction across a differential volume (W m^{-2}). It represents the number of photons available to be absorbed.
LVRPA	Local Volumetric Rate of Photon Absorption (W m^{-3}). Product of G by κ . It represents the absorbed energy in a differential volume.
A_E	Absorbed energy (W). Integral of LVRPA across a volume, measuring the total absorbed energy.
<i>Solar radiation variables</i>	
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiation (W m^{-2}). Flux of direct solar radiation measured in a surface normal to the direction of the incident light.
DHI	Diffuse Horizontal Irradiation (W m^{-2}). Flux of diffuse solar radiation measured in a horizontal surface.
lat	Latitude ($^\circ$)
<i>Concentration factors</i>	
CF	Concentration Factor (dimensionless). Ratio between flux reaching the reacting tube and flux reaching the collectors opening, considering reflectivity 1.0 and direct radiation normal to the opening surface of the collector.
$DCF(\alpha)$	Dynamic Concentration Factor (dimensionless). Ratio between average incident radiation in the reacting tube and flux reaching the collectors opening, depending on reflectivity, optical density and incidence angle.
$DCF_q(\alpha)$	Dynamic Concentration Factor of flux (dimensionless). Ratio between flux reaching the reacting tube and flux reaching the collectors opening, depending on reflectivity, optical density and incidence angle.
$DCF_{dif}(\alpha)$	Dynamic Concentration Factor of diffuse radiation (dimensionless). Ratio between average incident radiation in the reacting tube and flux reaching the collectors opening, depending on reflectivity and optical density.

treatment is designed with a CF of 1.0, corresponding to an acceptance angle of 90° . This acceptance angle means it is theoretically capable of capturing all the incident radiation for all the solar beam angles, independently on the geolocations, season, and daily Earth rotation. However, that does not necessarily mean that CPC with CF of 1.0 always represents the optimal design for any geocoordinates. This work aims to prove that, for specific locations, the use of CPC with higher CF could be a better choice, as the sacrifice of a small number of solar rays with high inclination angles could be counteracted by the improvement due to the concentration of predominant beam angles.

The CF is defined as the ratio between the radiation flux reaching the reactor and that reaching the collector. Assuming that all the incident radiation within the range of accepted angles is ideally reflected to the reactor, the flux ratio is usually simplified to a geometric relation [23]. However, we will prove that this simplification can only be applied to ideal reflector material with a high value of reflectivity. For non-ideal reflector surfaces, the ratio between fluxes would change with the incidence angle, and a single CF value cannot correctly describe the collector behaviour. Therefore, the collector performance becomes dependent not only on the CF value, but also on the dynamics of the incident beam angles associated with the variation of the solar vector at the specific geolocation.

Moreover, the reaction rate of photochemical processes depends on the absorbed energy in the reactor, proportional to the volumetric incident radiation and not necessarily to the incident flux at the reactor surface. For systems with high optical density (OD), such as those

employed in semiconductor photocatalysis or photo-Fenton water treatment processes, a full absorption of the incoming radiation is expected, being the absorbed energy proportional to the flux. However, as the absorptivity of the medium decreases, the absorbed energy becomes more dependent on the path length. Therefore, for low OD systems, such as those involved in solar water disinfection (SODIS), a CF based on fluxes cannot correctly account for the optical phenomena that condition the process efficiency, even considering the reflector material and the variation of the incident beam angle.

To overcome these limitations, in this work, we present the definition of a novel parameter called dynamic concentration factor (DCF) to describe the efficiency of a solar CPC rigorously. This parameter takes into account the actual optical effectiveness of the system, including the reflectivity of the material and the OD of the reactor medium. The DCF is defined as the ratio between the average incident radiation in the reactor and the radiation flux reaching the receiver. Therefore, it represents an accurate calculation of the collector efficiency for photochemical processes regardless of its location, date-time and optical properties. A simple methodology based on a ray-tracing tool (made openly available) has been developed to calculate the DCF . Successful validation of the tool has been done with simulation using a high precision model based on the discrete ordinate method and with actinometry experimental data of CPC with different acceptance angles. Finally, worldwide time-varying solar irradiation data were used to carry out a comparative analysis to determine the optimal CPC for a specific geolocation.

Fig. 1. Geometric profile of a CPC reactor.

2. Material and methods

2.1. CPC photoreactors

The profile of a CPC presents two different sections: an involute around the receiver tube and a parabolic section (Fig. 1) [24]. The involute is defined by the points in which the normal is tangent to the receiver tube's external circumference (R). The Cartesian coordinates of the involute in the (x, y) plane as a function of the angular coordinate (φ) are given by Eqs. (1) and (2) [21]:

$$x = R \cdot (\sin\varphi - \varphi \cdot \cos\varphi) \tag{1}$$

$$y = -R \cdot (\varphi \cdot \sin\varphi + \cos\varphi) \tag{2}$$

The parabolic section consists of two symmetric parabolas whose optical axes form an angle θ concerning the collector axis, called acceptance angle. Each parabola extends until its surface is parallel to the vertical axis of the CPC. The coordinates of the parabolic segment are given by Eqs. (3) and (4):

$$x = R \cdot (\sin\varphi - B \cdot \cos\varphi) \tag{3}$$

$$y = -R \cdot (B \cdot \sin\varphi + \cos\varphi) \tag{4}$$

Where B is a variable that depends on the angle of acceptance θ and can be calculated using Eq. (5):

Fig. 2. Geometric profile of CPC reactors for different concentration factors (CF) and acceptance angles (θ) for the same tube diameter.

Table 1

Dimensions of a CPC with a receiver tube 26 mm in diameter and 380 mm in length for different acceptance angles.

CF	θ (°)	Aperture width (cm)	Height (cm)	Collector surface (m ²)
1	90	8.17	3.34	0.049
1.03	75	8.46	4.52	0.058
1.15	60	9.43	6.27	0.072
1.41	45	11.55	9.66	0.100
2	30	16.34	18.79	0.174
3.86	15	31.56	65.96	0.545

$$B = \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} + \theta + \varphi - \cos(\varphi - \theta)}{1 + \sin(\varphi - \theta)} \quad (5)$$

The CPC profile can be calculated using the expression of the involute and the parabola, whose limits depends on the acceptance angle:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{If } 0 \leq \varphi \leq \frac{\pi}{2} + \theta \rightarrow \text{Equations 1 and 2} \\ \text{If } \frac{\pi}{2} + \theta < \varphi \leq \frac{3\pi}{2} - \theta \rightarrow \text{Equations 3 and 4} \end{array} \right. \quad (6)$$

In general, the concentration factor (CF) for a solar collector is defined as the relationship between the radiation flux that reaches the receiver tube and the radiation flux that reaches the collector's opening area [25]. The CF is commonly approximated to the ratio between the opening area (A_0) and the area of the receiver (A_r) according to the following equation [26]:

$$CF = \frac{A_0}{A_r} = \frac{A_0}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot R} \quad (7)$$

For a CPC, the CF can be expressed as a function of the acceptance angle:

$$CF = \frac{1}{\sin(\theta)} \quad (8)$$

CPC reactors with concentration factors of 1, 1.03, 1.15, 1.41, 2 and 3.86 corresponding to θ of 90°, 75°, 60°, 45°, 30° and 15°, respectively, were designed and studied (Fig. 2). In all cases, the diameter of the receiver tube was set to 26 mm. Table 1 shows the main dimensions of the studied reactors.

Model predictions were validated with experimental data using CPC reactors with θ of 90°, 60° and 30°. The CPC reactors were manufactured using a 3D printer and subsequently coated with aluminium tape as a reflector material, following the procedure shown elsewhere [27]. The total length was 380 mm, and the reflectivity of the material was 0.7.

2.2. Experimental methods

A large-scale solar simulator based on a xenon lamp (OSRAM XBO 5000 W/H XL OFR) was used as a light source to simulate the solar spectrum [28]. The CPC reactors were placed at a fixed distance from the light source to ensure reproducibility in the irradiance. The CPCs were tilted with different angles regarding the incident light to simulate different solar vectors, as shown in Fig. 3.

The CPC's optical efficiency was evaluated by quantifying the total incident radiation reaching the receiver tube using potassium

ferrioxalate actinometry reactions according to the methodology described elsewhere [29]. The actinometrical solution was recirculated through the reactor using a centrifugal pump (Model NH-50PX-X, Pan World Co., Ltd.) connected to a reservoir tank. The total illuminated volume was 0.2 L, whereas the total volume was 2 L.

2.3. Ray-tracing

A ray-tracing represents illustratively the path that rays follow from the opening plane of a CPC reactor until they leave the collector. To obtain it, a computer tool capable of calculating the path of the rays depending on their inclination and the reflector geometry was developed using the widely accessible Microsoft Excel software. This tool is available as Supplementary Information and at an online repository [30].

A 2D geometry must be provided to the Excel tool of both the reflector and the reactor. The user can also choose the number of rays traced, their incidence angle, and the reflectivity coefficient of the reflector. Rays are evenly distributed, starting from an emission line at an arbitrary height and the same width as the reactor. The starting point of the emission line is calculated to place the first ray in the left end of the reactor. Each ray can specularly bounce in the reflector any number of times, crossing or not the reactor in its path, to finally leave the region when it crosses the upper opening plane of the reflector geometry again.

Radiation intensity at emission line is treated as constant, with a value of 1 W m⁻¹, or 1 W m⁻² if a depth of 1 m is considered in the z-axis. Thus, incident radiation carried by rays in W m⁻² equals the ray width. Every time a ray is reflected by the collector, its carried energy is reduced using the reflectivity of the material. Similarly, due to the absorption of the reaction medium, the rays lose energy along their path through the interior of the receiver tube. Both effects are described in Eqs. (9) and (10):

$$E_a = E_b e^{-\kappa L} \quad (9)$$

$$E_a = E_b r \quad (10)$$

Where E_b and E_a are the intensity of the ray before and after crossing the reactor (Eq. (9)) and before and after bouncing in the collector (Eq. (10)). κ is the absorption coefficient, L the path length across the reactor and r the reflectivity of the collector material.

The sensitivity of the result is largely dependent on the number of traced rays. When a too low number of rays is traced, the result is highly dependent on this number, as there are different distributions, and the approximation of area covered in the reactor to a rectangle (length by width) cannot be applied. The calculus time of the tool rises with the number of rays, so a balance between precision and time must be chosen. A study of the values of each reactor with a different number of rays was carried out (results in Fig. S1), choosing a final value of 200, where results seem to be stable.

Simulations for CPC with different acceptance angles were carried out for beam angles in the range of 0 to 90° with a 1° step. The effect of the reflectivity of the material used for the construction of the collector was also studied for values between 0 and 1 with a step of 0.1. On the other hand, with the aim of applying the results obtained to different photoactivated processes, the DCF was calculated for different optical densities of the reaction medium. An OD value of 0.0 (negligible

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the actinometrical experiments carried out with the CPC reactors for different beam angles (α).

Fig. 4. Ray-tracing for a CPC reactor with $CF = 1$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$ for different beam angles (α) of (a) 0° , (b) 15° , (c) 30° , (d) 45° , (e) 60° and (f) 75° . See supplementary information for the results of CPC reactors with other CF values.

absorption) is assimilable to a SODIS process [31], while an OD value of 10 corresponds to catalytic processes such as photo-Fenton [13] and TiO_2 photocatalysis [32] was set. Additionally, to validate the results of the simulations, DCF values were also calculated for an OD value of 3.6, corresponding to the ferrioxalate actinometry reactions that were carried out experimentally.

2.4. Estimation of worldwide time-varying solar irradiation

A computational tool previously developed [33] was used to generate data of direct normal irradiation (DNI), diffuse horizontal irradiation (DHI), and solar vector, for every location in a 0.5° grid (both in latitude and longitude), between polar circles (almost $6 \cdot 10^5$ points), and 80 timesteps between sunrise and sunset during the 15th day of each month (total of $5.56 \cdot 10^7$ combinations).

CPCs of different opening angles (15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75° and 90°) and a constant 0.013 m inner radius and 1 m long tube were evaluated using DCF values at each location. For comparison purposes, a target treatment flow of 1000 L day^{-1} and reference doses of 3.5 kWh m^{-2} for OD 0.0 and 0.21 kWh m^{-2} for OD 10.0 were used, corresponding to 4 bacterial inactivation logs for solar disinfection and solar photo fenton disinfection processes, respectively [13]. Based on this reference scenario, it is possible to calculate for each of the studied collectors what would be the necessary reactor volume, the required reactor surface (area projected on the ground considering that the reactor inclination equals its latitude), and the total cost according to the following equations:

$$Volume = 1000 \cdot \frac{Reference\ Dose}{Average\ Daily\ Dose} \quad (11)$$

$$Projected\ area = \frac{Width \cdot \cos(Lat) + Height \cdot \sin(Lat)}{Tube\ section} \cdot Volume \quad (12)$$

$$Cost = Tube\ cost + Reflector\ cost \times Collector\ area \quad (13)$$

Where *Projected area* in Eq. (12) is calculated considering the inclination of the reactor to maximize collection, that equals location latitude, while *Collector area* in Eq. (13) is the product of the collector perimeter by the tube and collector length, using a 1 m reference length.

The cost of the tube was established at 10.05 € m^{-1} , while the cost of the collector was established at 22.55 € m^{-2} . The tube cost was estimated using a reference 0.13 m diameter tube, 2.5 mm thickness, according to the price offered by Huailai Golden Glass Co., Ltd. The aluminium cost represents 4 mm thickness sheets, according to the price offered by Henan Xintai Aluminum Industry Co., Ltd. Collector perimeter, calculated for a 0.13 m tube to get the collector area, is proportional to the tube diameter. Prices will keep their proportion at different tube diameters and will lead to the same results in the costs comparison.

3. Results

3.1. Ray-tracing

Fig. 4 shows the ray-tracing for a CPC reactor with $CF = 1$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$ for different beam angles, while Figs. S2-S6 in the supplementary material present the ray-tracing for the rest of the studied reactors with θ of 75° , 60° , 45° , 30° and 15° , respectively. For $\theta = 90^\circ$, Fig. 4a–d show that for α between 0° and 45° , the number of rays reaching the receiver tube without bouncing in the collector is essentially the same. However, in Fig. 4e it can be observed how for $\alpha = 60^\circ$ a blank region appears with

Fig. 5. Incident radiation in a reactor without a reflector (a), with a reflector in a non-absorbing medium (b) and a full-absorbing medium (c).

rays blocked by the collector surface. This blank region grows for $\alpha = 75^\circ$ (Fig. 4f) and would be total for 90° (not shown). The same region appears at lower angles in Figs. S2–S6, as detailed in Fig. 6. The same number of rays was used in every collector, and thus, the concentration seems equal in all of them, but the opening area of collectors grows as the acceptance angle decreases, and each ray represents a larger area and carries more energy.

On the other hand, the number of rays that bounces in the reflecting surface more than once before entering the receiver tube strongly depends on θ , ranging from approximately one-third in Fig. 4a ($\alpha = 0^\circ$) to none in Fig. 4f ($\alpha = 75^\circ$), where half of the rays reach the receiver tube without bouncing, and the other half bounces only once. As the number of bounces increases, the effect of the collector reflectivity coefficient grows in importance because for the non-ideal reflection in real materials, every bounce means energy loss.

Finally, the path length of each ray across the receiver tube also depends on the incidence angle of the rays. Therefore, the amount of energy absorbed by the medium on the receiver is also impacted by α , being the impact different depending on the absorptivity and therefore the OD of the medium.

3.2. Dynamic concentration factor (DCF)

This novel parameter is defined to accurately describe the concentration efficiency of solar collectors considering the geometry and the radiation incidence angle, reflector material properties, and light absorption of the reactor medium.

Classic CF is usually defined as the geometric relationship between the area exposed and the size of the reactor (Eq. (7)). However, this definition of the concentration is only accurate for ideal materials with total reflectivity, whereas in real applications materials usually present reflectivity value below 85%. As shown in Fig. 4 (and Figs. S2–S6), the path that each ray follows is significantly dependent on the collector geometry and the beam angle (α). Both the number of bounces (and its associated losses of energy due to non-ideal reflection) and the path lengths of rays crossing the reactor strongly depend on the direction of the incident photons.

A first attempt to improve the accuracy of the calculation of the CF would include the effect of the non-ideal reflectivity of the materials. Assuming a total absorption on the reactor tube, the flux-based dynamic concentration factor (DCF_q) would be defined as shown in Eq. (14) (detailed derivation in Appendix A.1):

$$DCF_q(\alpha) = \frac{(\text{Flux receiver tube } (W \text{ m}^{-2}))}{(\text{Flux CPC opening plane } (W \text{ m}^{-2}))} \quad (14)$$

$$DCF_q(\alpha) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (r^{b_i(\alpha)})}{n \sin\theta}$$

Where n is the number of traced rays, r is the reflectivity of the collector, b is the number of bounces of each ray (dependent on the beam angle, α), and θ is the acceptance angle of the collector. The total absorption condition in the reactor tube volume means that bounces of each ray are only computed before hitting the reactor tube, as once entering the reactor, it is absorbed.

The situation changes significantly when non-absorbing media are considered. Although flux and incident radiation are sometimes used interchangeably, they are not the same. Fig. 5 represents the impact of the presence of a flat reflector on the incident radiation depending on the absorption of the medium. Fig. 5b shows how a reflector in a non-absorbing medium doubles the incident radiation (rays with constant intensity have a double path length). In contrast, the presence of a flat reflector in a full-absorbing has a negligible effect (Fig. 5c). As the photons are absorbed, the ray intensity decreases, and the increased path length has a minor effect on the total incident radiation (reflected rays don't carry enough energy enough to modify the incident radiation value substantially).

If an irradiance of 100 W m^{-2} at the top surface is considered for every case in Fig. 5, the incident radiation would also be 100 W m^{-2} in Fig. 5a, whereas it would double to 200 W m^{-2} in Fig. 5b with an ideal reflector of 100% reflectivity (100 W m^{-2} crossing twice each point of the reactor). In contrast, the average incident radiation in Fig. 5c would be much lower than 100 W m^{-2} , independently of the presence or absence of the reflector. In other words, as photons are absorbed when crossing the reactor, flat reflectors are meaningless for full-absorbing systems. Similarly, total absorption also reduces the relevance of path length: rays crossing the reactor diameter in Fig. 5a or b have a higher contribution to the incident radiation than rays crossing shorter chords, while in Fig. 5c all rays have a similar contribution independently on the chord length. Of course, systems with intermediate absorption should be analyzed in terms of the OD (absorption coefficient multiplied by the path length), and a partial effect of the reflector would be expected.

This difference between flux (amount of energy passes through a surface) and incident radiation (availability of photons in a volume) is of particular importance in photochemical processes, as the energy absorption determines the reaction kinetics, and this is proportional to the incident radiation in the volume, not to the flux in the external tube surface. Consequently, the accurate definition of the DCF must be done

Fig. 6. Definition of the shadow region in the CPC with an acceptance angle of $\theta = 45^\circ$.

in terms of the incident radiation, representing the capability of the collector to make the solar irradiance available for the photochemical process (Eq. (15), see detailed derivation in Appendix A.2):

$$DCF(\alpha) = \frac{\text{Average incident radiation } (W m^{-2})}{\text{Incoming flux } (W m^{-2})} \quad (15)$$

$$DCF(\alpha) = \frac{\Delta x \sum r^{b_j} (1 - \exp(-\kappa L_{i_j}(\alpha))) \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \exp(-\kappa L_{i_{j,k}}(\alpha))}{\kappa \pi R^2}$$

Where $L_i(\alpha)$ is the ray path across the tube, and $L_{i,j}(\alpha)$ is the path length at bounce j . Δx is the distance between emitted rays in the x-axis, r is the material reflectivity coefficient, b is the number of bounces of the rays in the reflector before reaching the tube, κ is the absorption coefficient, and R is the radius of the reactor tube. DCF is calculated using the area-averaged incident radiation in the reactor.

To ease the analysis of the calculated DCF values for 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75° and 90° CPCs, α from 0° to θ (1° step), reflectivity from 0 to 1 (0.1 step) and zero absorption are presented in Figs. S7–S12 in the supplementary material. This data collection allows the prediction of intermediate scenarios through interpolation with minor deviation in a short time.

Values below 1.0 are caused by the shadow of the collector over the reactor at the high incidence angles. The size of this shaded region equals the angle between two lines tangent to the reactor starting from one of the collector ends (see Fig. 6). Rays with an incident angle (α) below the green one ($\alpha = 0^\circ$ means vertical rays) enter the collector and are redirected to the reactor. Rays with α over θ are unable to reach the reactor and are bounced back. In the shaded region, between green and red angles, some rays enter the collector and reach the reactor, while the remaining ones are blocked by the outer collector surface.

In Fig. 7a the whole set of values obtained for each CPC reactor is represented, including reflectivity values between 0.0 and 1.0. This figure allows a more straightforward comparison and selection of the most suitable reactor depending on the range of values of acceptance angles for solar radiation in each specific location. Fig. 7b and 7c show the same approach but calculated for OD values of 3.6 (corresponding to ferrioxalate actinometry experiments) and 10 (for photo-Fenton and TiO_2 photocatalytic processes). On the other hand, in Figs. S7–S24 of the supplementary material, a collection of DCF data is presented for all OD values.

The shaded areas in Fig. 7 represent the range of values of the DCF depending on the reflectivity, from 0 (the bottom end of the area) to 1.0 (the upper end of the area).

As stated before, at high values of OD , almost all the incident radiation is absorbed as it enters the reactor, and the DCF is proportional to the DCF_q according to the expression given by Eq. (16) (detailed derivation in Appendix B). As it can be observed in Fig. 7c, with an OD of 10

Fig. 7. DCF as a function of the beam angle (α) for CPC with different acceptance angles (θ) and reflectivity (r) of the collector surface ranging from 0.0 to 1.0 for: a) a non-absorbing medium (OD of 0.0); b) a medium with an OD of 3.6; and c) a medium with an OD of 10 in the reactor tube.

(99.99% of the radiation is absorbed), the DCF keeps a constant value in each reactor, 0.4 times the value of the DCF_q . If the collector reflectivity is 1.0, the DCF_q would equal the traditional CF .

$$DCF_q = \frac{DCF \cdot OD}{4} \quad (16)$$

Once the DCF values for a given reflectivity and absorption value are calculated in a reactor, the average value between beam angles would be

Fig. 8. DCF_{dif} values for the studied reactors between reflectivity 0.0 and 1.0 for an OD of a) 0; b) 3.6; and c) 10.

the dynamic concentration factor value for diffuse incident radiation (DCF_{dif}). This allows calculating the contribution of diffuse radiation in the process and estimating the total incident radiation in cloudy days according to Eq. (17):

$$G_{tube} = DCF(\alpha) \cdot DNI \cdot \cos\alpha + DCF_{dif} \cdot DHI \quad (17)$$

Where DNI is the Direct Normal Irradiation (Parallel fraction of solar radiation measured normal to the ray direction), DHI is the Diffuse Horizontal Irradiation (Diffuse fraction of solar radiation measured as its flux in a horizontal surface), and DCF_{dif} is the Dynamic Concentration

Fig. 9. Incident radiation reaching the receiver tube versus (a) beam angle, (b) dynamic concentration factor, and (c) predicted incident radiation using DCF and CF .

Factor of the incident radiation for diffuse sources, calculated using Eq. (18) (derivation detailed in Appendix A.3).

$$DCF_{dif} = \frac{1}{\pi} \sum_0^\theta DCF(\alpha) \cos\alpha \quad (18)$$

Fig. 8a shows the DCF_{dif} values for the studied reactors at different reflectivity factors for an OD value of 0.0. All the reactors show similar concentration values of diffuse sunlight, meaning that, in cloudy

Fig. 10. Average annual incident radiation reached in the receiving tube worldwide using CPC reactors with different acceptance angles for an OD of 0.0 (top), and 10 (bottom).

Fig. 11. Best CPC reactor worldwide as a function of the volume required for OD of 0.0 and 10.

regions, the 90° standard CPC would be the best choice, as it has a lower surface and covered area. Similarly, Fig. 8b and c show DCF_{diff} for OD values of 3.6 and 10, respectively, showing similar trends that in the case of OD of 0.0.

3.3. Actinometric reactions

Experimental validation of the radiation concentration efficiency of different CPCs predicted by the DCF has been carried out by ferrioxalate actinometry experiments. Reactors with θ of 90° , 60° and 30° were designed and manufactured. A large-scale solar simulator has been used as a light source with different incident beam angles, as shown in Fig. 3.

In Fig. 9a it is possible to observe how a decrease in θ causes the inability to concentrate the solar rays with higher α . Nevertheless, it produces a significant increase in the concentrating capacity for the less inclined solar rays. This aspect must be considered when choosing the optimal solar concentrator to be used since there are certain areas of the planet where the variation in solar α throughout the year is minimal, and a CPC reactor with a small θ could significantly increase the overall efficiency of the system. On the other hand, Fig. 9b shows a linear relationship, regardless of the CPC used, between the experimental values of incident radiation obtained by actinometry and the DCF values calculated for a reflectivity of 0.68, an OD of 3.6 and the corresponding

α). In contrast, the CF uses a single value per collector, unable to capture the effect on the collecting ability of the α , as can be seen in Fig. 9c. Therefore, it is undoubtedly confirmed that the use of the DCF provides more accurate predictions of the concentration efficiency of each collector than the classical geometrical CF.

3.4. Worldwide CPC evaluation

Once the DCF were obtained for the different collectors, an evaluation of the optimal θ in the different locations of the planet was carried out based on three fundamental aspects: volume of reactor used, surface occupied by the collector and total cost.

Once these data have been obtained and using the calculated DCF and DCF_{diff} values, it is possible to obtain the incident radiation that would reach the receiving tube in the different geographical areas of the planet with the different CPCs using Eq. (17). The average monthly dose was calculated as the sum of the obtained values multiplied by the time step. Finally, the average annual dose is calculated as the sum of the monthly average values by its number of days, divided by 365. The results for OD values of 0.0 and 10 are shown in Fig. 10.

Figs. S25-S30 in the supplementary information show the results obtained in each case, while Figs. 11 and 12 show the world map coloured depending on which reactor has the lowest requirements for each

Fig. 12. Best CPC reactor worldwide as a function of the required cost for OD of 0.0 and 10.

of the parameters studied for both OD 0.0 and 10.

For the required reactor volume, Fig. 11 shows how for both OD values, the reactor with $\theta = 90^\circ$ is the best choice in the areas close to the equator (latitudes between -12° and $+12^\circ$), where the midday zenith angle of the Sun shows the highest variation along the year and the average cloud cover is relatively high. The higher the latitude, the smaller variation in midday zenith angle. Thus, collectors with $\theta = 60^\circ$ and 75° require the lowest volume for latitudes in the range between 12° and 25° , following a direct correlation with the latitude due to the low average cloud cover in these regions. For latitudes above 25° , the collector with $\theta = 30^\circ$ provides the best ratio between collected radiation and volume, whereas for the highest latitude range, the collector with $\theta = 15^\circ$ leads to the best results. The frontier between these two collectors does not show a clear pattern with latitude due to the differences in average cloud cover, and differs for optical density 0.0 and 10.0. It is essential to highlight that for OD of 0.0, in the areas where the $\theta = 15^\circ$ CPC is used, a reduction of 30–50% in the required volume compared to the classic $\theta = 90^\circ$ CPC is estimated, whereas, in the regions using intermediate collectors, the reduction in the required volume is in the order of 5–10%.

Regarding the required surface, the results show that, due to its smaller dimensions, the CPC with $\theta = 90^\circ$ is the most suitable on the entire planet for both OD values.

Finally, if the total cost is considered (Fig. 12), for both OD values, the CPC with $\theta = 15^\circ$ is not suitable for any location due to the high

collector area required. For the $\theta = 30^\circ$ CPC, the reduction in volume compensates the increase in the required surface on latitudes above 45° , where the maximum midday zenith angle of the Sun shows minor variation, obtaining reductions in the total cost up to 7% for OD of 0.0 and up to 6% for OD of 10 compared to the $\theta = 90^\circ$ CPC. Intermediate collectors seem to be optimal in different latitude bands between 45° and 25° . In contrast, in the equatorial region between 25° north and 25° south, the $\theta = 90^\circ$ CPC provides the best results in terms of required volume, area, and cost.

Finally, as far as cost is concerned, it is important to note that this study focuses only on CPC-type solar collectors. Some researchers have suggested the possibility of using simplified geometries [34–36]. Future analysis of these simplified collectors based on the DCF could provide insights into the optimal system for different regions of the planet from the cost optimization point of view.

4. Conclusions

The main parameter that defines a CPC reactor is the concentration factor. However, this work proves that the traditional geometrical definition of this parameter does not adequately represent the concentration efficiency of a CPC operating under different irradiation conditions. In contrast, the newly defined dynamic concentration factor (DCF) has been shown to successfully calculate the concentration efficiency of CPC for different solar beam angles. Its calculation has been validated by

ray-tracing simulations and experimentally by actinometry. Besides, DCF values for different conditions were presented, which is very useful when designing CPC reactors, allowing the calculation of real concentration efficiencies regardless of the location, time of day, or season of the year.

The DCF values for different CPCs allow a more in-depth study of the optimal collector in a given location, considering the direct/diffuse light distribution and the sun path over the year. Based on that, it is concluded that the widespread use of the $\theta = 90^\circ$ CPC could not be the best option for specific regions, depending on the parameter chosen for the selection (volume, collection surface or cost).

Finally, it must be noted that the use of DCF values can also be extrapolated to thermoactivated processes and those with temperature-radiation synergy, where the increase in temperature in the reactor tube could also be predicted.

Appendix A. . Calculus of dynamic concentration factors

A.1. DCF flux

To estimate the proportion between the flux reaching the receiver tube and the one entering the collector opening, the contribution of each ray must be considered:

Radiation flow contribution of a single ray in the collector opening = $E \cos \alpha \Delta x$

Radiation flow contribution of a single ray in the receiver tube = $E \cos \alpha \Delta x r^{b_i(\alpha)}$

Where E is the radiation intensity of each ray measured in a plane normal to the ray direction, α is the incidence angle of the ray, Δx is the width of each ray in the collector opening (the division of the opening length over the number of rays), r is the collectors material reflectivity, and b is the number of bounces of the ray i before reaching the receiver tube, as a function of the incidence angle.

A total absorption inside the reactor tube is considered in the flux estimation. Therefore, only the first time a ray crosses the reactor is included in the equation.

The flow in each surface is calculated as the ratio between the sum of radiation flow contributions and the surface area. The relation between areas is the traditional CF (concentration factor), equal to $\sin^{-1} \theta$, being θ the acceptance angle of the collector:

$$DCF_q(\alpha) = \frac{\text{Flux reaching the receiver tube } (Wm^{-2})}{\text{Flux reaching the CPC opening plane } (Wm^{-2})}$$

$$DCF_q(\alpha) = \frac{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (r^{b_i(\alpha)} E \Delta x \cos \alpha)}{\text{Tube perimeter}}}{\frac{n E \Delta x \cos \alpha}{\text{Opening length}}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (r^{b_i(\alpha)})}{n \sin \theta}$$

A.2. DCF incident radiation

The Dynamic Concentration Factor of Incident Radiation is calculated as the proportion between the average incident radiation in the receiver tube and the flux in the collectors opening. The average is calculated from the contribution of each ray. The first time a ray reaches the receiver tube, its intensity is $E r^{b_i(\alpha)}$. After crossing the tube, the intensity is $E r^{b_i(\alpha)} \exp(-\kappa L_i(\alpha))$, where κ is the absorption coefficient of the reaction media, and L_i is the path length of the ray across the tube. The m^{th} time a ray crosses the reactor, the intensity is $E r^{b_i(\alpha)} \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \exp(-\kappa L_{i,j})$, including the reduction in the intensity in each path. If measured inside the reaction media, the intensity decreases as $E r^{b_i(\alpha)} \exp(-\kappa x) \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \exp(-\kappa L_{i,j})$, where x is the distance travelled across the tube.

Thus, using as a coordinate system the one shown in Fig. A1 (x is the distance from the entering point following the ray direction, and y is the normal direction, along the ray width), the contribution of a given ray to the total incident radiation is:

$$\iint G_i = \iint E r^{b_i(\alpha)} \exp(-\kappa x) \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \exp(-\kappa L_{i,j}) dx dy$$

$$\iint G_i = \frac{E \Delta x \cos \alpha r^{b_i(\alpha)} (1 - \exp(-\kappa L_i(\alpha))) \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \exp(-\kappa L_{i,j})}{k}$$

Once obtained the contribution of each ray, the average incident radiation is calculated as the ratio of the sum of the rays contributions over the receiver tube section:

$$\frac{\sum \iint G_i}{\text{Tube section}} = \frac{E \Delta x \cos \alpha \sum r^{b_i(\alpha)} (1 - \exp(-\kappa L_i(\alpha))) \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \exp(-\kappa L_{i,j})}{\kappa \pi R^2}$$

And, finally, the DCF is the proportion between average incident radiation and incoming flux:

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Fig. A1.

$$DCF(\alpha) = \frac{\text{Average incident radiation in the receiver tube } (Wm^{-2})}{\text{Flux reaching theCPC opening plane } (Wm^{-2})}$$

$$DCF(\alpha) = \frac{E\Delta x \cos\alpha \sum r^{b_i(\alpha)} (1 - \exp(-\kappa L_i(\alpha))) \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \exp(-\kappa L_{i,k})}{\kappa \pi R^2 E \cos\alpha}$$

$$DCF(\alpha) = \frac{\Delta x \sum r^{b_i(\alpha)} (1 - \exp(-\kappa L_i(\alpha))) \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \exp(-\kappa L_{i,k})}{\kappa \pi R^2}$$

A.3. DCF diffuse incident radiation

The Dynamic Concentration Factor of Diffuse Incident Radiation (DCF_{dif}) is the proportion between the average incident radiation in the receiver tube and the flux of diffuse radiation in the collectors opening. Diffuse radiation has an equal intensity in each direction, and the DCF_{dif} can be derived from known values of $DCF(\alpha)$ in a given reactor.

The contribution to the radiation flux of each direction depends on its angle with the collectors opening normal direction, but they have equal contribution to the incident radiation. Then, if $DCF(\alpha)$ is transformed to be a relation between incident radiation values (in the reacting tube and the collectors opening), the calculation reduces to an average. Those transformed DCF values are noted as DCF_G in the following equations.

To transform the $DCF(\alpha)$ values to $DCF_G(\alpha)$ a simple calculation must be carried out:

$$q = I \cos\alpha$$

$$G = I$$

$$DCF_G(\alpha) = DCF(\alpha) \frac{q}{G} = DCF(\alpha) \cos\alpha$$

Now, $DCF_{G,dif}$ can be calculated, again meaning a proportion between incident radiation values.

$$DCF_{G,dif} = \frac{1}{\theta} \sum_0^\theta DCF(\alpha) \cos\alpha$$

Finally, to get the value of DCF_{dif} , the relation between flux and incident radiation of diffuse radiation reaching the collectors opening must be considered. In the following equations, angle θ is the standard representation of zenith angle in spherical coordinates, and not the use in the rest of this work as acceptance angle of the collector:

$$q = \int I \cos(\theta) d\Omega = I \iint \cos(\theta) \sin(\theta) d\theta d\varphi = 2\pi I$$

$$G = \int I d\Omega = I \iint \sin(\theta) d\theta d\varphi = 4\pi I$$

$$G = 2q$$

In summary:

$$DCF_{dif} = DCF_{G,dif} \frac{G}{q} = 2 DCF_{G,dif} = \frac{1}{\pi} \sum_0^\theta DCF(\alpha) \cos\alpha$$

Appendix B. Derivation of the relation between DCF and DCF_q under high optical density conditions.

The product of the incident radiation (G , $W\ m^{-2}$) by the absorption coefficient (κ , m^{-1}) is the local volumetric rate of photon absorption (LVRPA, $W\ m^{-3}$). The integral of this magnitude along the reactor volume gives the total absorbed energy (A_E , W).

$$A_E = \int^V LVRPA\ dV = \int^V G\ \kappa\ dV$$

On the other hand, the integral of the flux (q , $W\ m^{-2}$) along the external reactor area gives the total flow of incoming energy (Q , W).

$$Q = \int^A q\ dA$$

If total absorption is considered, both terms are equal ($A_E = Q$), as all the incoming energy (Q), is absorbed (A_E).

$$\int^V G\ \kappa\ dV = \int^A q\ dA$$

$$G\kappa z\pi r^2 = qz2\pi r$$

$$Q = \frac{G \cdot OD}{4}$$

Therefore:

$$DCF_Q = \frac{DCF \cdot OD}{4}$$

Appendix C. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.135360>.

References

- [1] Y. Zhang, M. Sivakumar, S. Yang, K. Enever, M. Ramezani-pour, Application of solar energy in water treatment processes: A review, *Desalination* 428 (2018) 116–145, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2017.11.020>.
- [2] V. Prashanth, P. Jayasree, P. Rajput, N. Remya, Solar photocatalysis and its application for emerging contaminant removal from wastewater, in: *Adv. Oxid. Process. Effl. Treat. Plants*, Elsevier, 2021: pp. 69–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-821011-6.00004-9>.
- [3] A. Dutta, N. Das, D. Sarkar, S. Chakrabarti, Development and characterization of a continuous solar-collector-reactor for wastewater treatment by photo-Fenton process, *Sol. Energy*. 177 (2019) 364–373, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2018.11.036>.
- [4] M. Rodríguez, J. Bussi, M. Andrea De León, Application of pillared raw clay-base catalysts and natural solar radiation for water decontamination by the photo-Fenton process, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 259 (2021) 118167, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2020.118167>.
- [5] A. Cabrera-Reina, A.B. Martínez-Piernas, Y. Bertakis, N.P. Xekoukoulotakis, A. Agüera, J.a. Sánchez Pérez, TiO₂ photocatalysis under natural solar radiation for the degradation of the carbapenem antibiotics imipenem and meropenem in aqueous solutions at pilot plant scale, *Water Res.* 166 (2019), 115037, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2019.115037>.
- [6] K. Kowalska, M. Roccamante, A. Cabrera Reina, P. Plaza-Bolaños, I. Oller, S. Malato, Pilot-scale removal of microcontaminants by solar-driven photo-Fenton in treated municipal effluents: Selection of operating variables based on lab-scale experiments, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9 (1) (2021) 104788, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.104788>.
- [7] W.F.D. Vilela, A. Minillo, O. Rocha, E.M. Vieira, E.B. Azevedo, Degradation of [D-Leu]-Microcystin-LR by solar heterogeneous photocatalysis (TiO₂), *Sol. Energy*. 86 (9) (2012) 2746–2752, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2012.06.012>.
- [8] K.G. McGuigan, R.M. Conroy, H.J. Mosler, M. du Preez, E. Ubomba-Jaswa, P. Fernandez-Ibañez, Solar water disinfection (SODIS): A review from bench-top to roof-top, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 235–236 (2012) 29–46, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2012.07.053>.
- [9] S. Helali, M.I. Polo-López, P. Fernández-Ibañez, B. Ohtani, F. Amano, S. Malato, C. Guillard, Solar photocatalysis: A green technology for E. coli contaminated water disinfection. Effect of concentration and different types of suspended catalyst, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A Chem.* 276 (2014) 31–40, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotochem.2013.11.011>.
- [10] P. Ozores Diez, S. Giannakis, J. Rodríguez-Chueca, D.a. Wang, B. Quilty, R. Devery, K. McGuigan, C. Pulgarin, Enhancing solar disinfection (SODIS) with the photo-Fenton or the Fe²⁺/peroxymonosulfate-activation process in large-scale plastic bottles leads to toxicologically safe drinking water, *Water Res.* 186 (2020) 116387, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.116387>.
- [11] M. Figueredo-Fernández, S. Gutiérrez-Alfaro, A. Acevedo-Merino, M.A. Manzano, Estimating lethal dose of solar radiation for enterococcus inactivation through radiation reaching the water layer. Application to Solar Water Disinfection (SODIS), *Sol. Energy*. 158 (2017) 303–310, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2017.09.006>.
- [12] Á. García-Gil, A. Martínez, M.I. Polo-López, J. Marugán, Kinetic modeling of the synergistic thermal and spectral actions on the inactivation of viruses in water by sunlight, *Water Res.* 183 (2020) 116074, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.116074>.
- [13] C. Casado, J. Moreno-SanSegundo, I. De la Obra, B. Esteban García, J.A. Sánchez Pérez, J. Marugán, Mechanistic modelling of wastewater disinfection by the photo-Fenton process at circumneutral pH, *Chem. Eng. J.* 403 (2021), 126335, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.126335>.
- [14] Á. García-Gil, C. Pablos, R.A. García-Muñoz, K.G. McGuigan, J. Marugán, Material selection and prediction of solar irradiance in plastic devices for application of solar water disinfection (SODIS) to inactivate viruses, bacteria and protozoa, *Sci. Total Environ.* 730 (2020) 139126, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139126>.
- [15] P.Y. Vorobiev, J. González-Hernández, Y. V. Vorobiev, Optimization of the solar energy collection in tracking and non-tracking photovoltaic solar system, in: 1st Int. Conf. Electr. Electron. Eng. ICEEE 2004 (2004) 310–314, <https://doi.org/10.1109/iceee.2004.1433900>.
- [16] M. Iqbal, Prediction of hourly diffuse solar radiation from measured hourly global radiation on a horizontal surface, *Sol. Energy*. 24 (5) (1980) 491–503, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X\(80\)90317-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X(80)90317-5).
- [17] M. Blal, S. Khelifi, R. Dabou, N. Sahouane, A. Slimani, A. Rouabhia, A. Ziane, A. Neçaibia, A. Bouraiou, B. Tidjar, A prediction models for estimating global solar radiation and evaluation meteorological effect on solar radiation potential under several weather conditions at the surface of Adrar environment, *Meas. J. Int. Meas. Confed.* 152 (2020) 107348, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2019.107348>.
- [18] A. Weiss, J.M. Norman, Partitioning solar radiation into direct and diffuse, visible and near-infrared components, *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 34 (2-3) (1985) 205–213, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1923\(85\)90020-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1923(85)90020-6).
- [19] A. Bohg, M. Briska, Solar energy collector, *IBM Tech. Disc. Bull.* 19 (1976) 2581–2582, <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-397270-5.00003-0>.
- [20] S. Malato Rodríguez, J. Blanco Gálvez, M.I. Maldonado Rubio, P. Fernández Ibañez, D. Alarcón Padilla, M. Collares Pereira, J. Farinha Mendes, J. Correia de Oliveira, Engineering of solar photocatalytic collectors, *Sol. Energy*. 77 (5) (2004) 513–524, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2004.03.020>.
- [21] I. Salgado-Tránsito, A.E. Jiménez-González, M.L. Ramón-García, C.A. Pineda-Arellano, C.A. Estrada-Gasca, I. Salgado Tránsito, A.E. Jiménez González, M. L. Ramón García, C.A. Pineda Arellano, C.A. Estrada Gasca, Design of a novel CPC collector for the photodegradation of carbaryl pesticides as a function of the solar concentration ratio, *Sol. Energy*. 115 (2015) 537–551, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2015.02.034>.

- [22] C. Casado, Á. García-Gil, R. van Grieken, J. Marugán, Critical role of the light spectrum on the simulation of solar photocatalytic reactors, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 252 (2019) 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2019.04.004>.
- [23] H. Zheng, Solar energy utilization and its collection devices, *Sol. Energy Desalin. Technol.* (2017) 47–171, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-805411-6.00002-6>.
- [24] R. Winston, H. Hinterberger, Principles of cylindrical concentrators for solar energy, *Sol. Energy.* 17 (4) (1975) 255–258, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X\(75\)90007-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X(75)90007-9).
- [25] L.T. Kostić, T.M. Pavlović, Z.T. Pavlović, Optimal design of orientation of PV/T collector with reflectors, *Appl. Energy.* 87 (10) (2010) 3023–3029, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2010.02.015>.
- [26] T. Osório, R. Pereira, A. Coelho, J. Marchã, J. Pereira, R. Silva, T. Eusébio, M. Collares-Pereira, A novel quasi-stationary CPC-type solar collector for intermediate temperature range applications for process heat: Simulation and experimental results, *AIP Conf. Proc.* (2019), 190012, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5117662>.
- [27] M. Martín-Sómer, J. Moreno-SanSegundo, C. Álvarez-Fernández, R. van Grieken, J. Marugán, High-performance low-cost solar collectors for water treatment fabricated with recycled materials, open-source hardware and 3d-printing technologies, *Sci. Total Environ.* 784 (2021), 147119, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147119>.
- [28] K.K. Philippe, R. Timmers, R. van Grieken, J. Marugán, Photocatalytic Disinfection and Removal of Emerging Pollutants from Effluents of Biological Wastewater Treatments, Using a Newly Developed Large-Scale Solar Simulator, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 55 (11) (2016) 2952–2958, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.5b04927>.
- [29] C.G. Hatchard, C.A. Parker, A new sensitive chemical actinometer. II. Potassium ferrioxalate as a standard chemical actinometer, *Proc. R. Soc. London. Ser. A. Math. Phys. Sci.* 235 (1956) 518 LP – 536. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1956.0102>.
- [30] J. Moreno-SanSegundo, M. Martín-Sómer, J. Marugán, Ray tracing tool, Rey Juan Carlos University, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788476>.
- [31] Á. García-Gil, R.A. García-Muñoz, K.G. McGuigan, J. Marugán, Solar water disinfection to produce safe drinking water, A review of parameters, enhancements, and modelling approaches to make SODIS faster and safer, *Molecules.* 26 (2021) 3431, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26113431>.
- [32] C. Casado, J. Marugán, R. Timmers, M. Muñoz, R. van Grieken, Comprehensive multiphysics modeling of photocatalytic processes by computational fluid dynamics based on intrinsic kinetic parameters determined in a differential photoreactor, *Chem. Eng. J.* 310 (2017) 368–380, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.07.081>.
- [33] J. Moreno-SanSegundo, S. Giannakis, S. Samoilii, G. Farinelli, K.G. McGuigan, C. Pulgarín, J. Marugán, SODIS potential: A novel parameter to assess the suitability of solar water disinfection worldwide, *Chem. Eng. J.* 419 (2021) 129889, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.129889>.
- [34] A.I. Gomes, T.F.C.V. Silva, M.A. Duarte, R.A.R. Boaventura, V.J.P. Vilar, Cost-effective solar collector to promote photo-Fenton reactions: A case study on the treatment of urban mature leachate, *J. Clean. Prod.* 199 (2018) 369–382, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.07.113>.
- [35] A. Martínez-García, M. Vincent, V. Rubiolo, M. Domingos, M.C. Canela, I. Oller, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, M.I. Polo-López, Assessment of a pilot solar V-trough reactor for solar water disinfection, *Chem. Eng. J.* 399 (2020) 125719, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.125719>.
- [36] T.F.C.V. Silva, P. Peri, A.S. Fajardo, L.O. Paulista, P.A. Soares, C.A. Martínez-Huitle, V.J.P. Vilar, Solar-driven heterogeneous photocatalysis using a static mixer as TiO₂-P25 support: Impact of reflector optics and material, *Chem. Eng. J.* 435 (2022) 134831, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.134831>.